

Cos4Cloud

Co-designing Citizen Observatories Services for the European Open Science Cloud

9 citizen science platforms focused on biodiversity and environmental monitoring are testing Cos4Cloud's cutting-edge technological services with their users.

Our goals:

Integrate citizen science into the **European Open Science Cloud landscape**.

Provide innovative user-centered services to the citizen observatories.

Facilitate the networking and knowledge management processes across organizations, people and initiatives working on citizen observatories.

Help ensure **the sustainability of citizen observatories**.

9 CITIZEN SCIENCE PLATFORMS INVOLVED

More about our services

- Two portals to integrate biodiversity and environmental observations coming from multiple citizen observatories in one place
- Artificial intelligence for identifying and locating species in a citizen science app
- A data model to standardise citizen science data
- An API to integrate Pl@ntNet's visual identification engine
- A tools repository to analyse and visualise all sorts of citizen science data
- A service to create integrative citizen science apps
- A do-it-yourself smart camera trap
- A website to filter and identify recordings and photos coming from camera traps
- A service that facilitates GDPR compliance
- A service to help reward citizen science users' contributions

Photo: Earthwatch, John Hunt

What is Cos4Cloud?

Cos4Cloud (Co-designed citizen observatories for the EOS-Cloud) aims to develop **thirteen technological services** to ensure the long-term viability of citizen science platforms - also known as citizen observatories - and help them reach a global scope. The project will make these services available on the new **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)**, a virtual space aimed at the European scientific community.

What do we offer?

A menu of thirteen new technological services to boost citizen science technologies. **The services have been co-designed with key stakeholders and are carefully being tested with final users.** Among other things, the cutting-edge technology will help improve interoperability, networking, data quality, and secure management of data within the citizen observatories.

Cos4Cloud is a project to boost citizen science technologies

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This project is part of:

COORDINATION

CONSORTIUM

<p>COLOMBIA</p>							
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PROJECT FACTS

Work programme: Horizon2020 - Duration: November 2019 – February 2023

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